

Diversity and conservation of Elm (*Ulmus*) genetic resources in Bulgaria

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Elms (*Ulmus* spp.) are highly valuable and important forest trees facing the risk of decline and genetic erosion due to the Dutch Elm disease. The natural genetic resources of *Ulmus* species in Bulgaria have deteriorated substantially during the second half of the 20th century. The main reason for the decline can be attributed to the Dutch Elm disease, but the human impact also contributed by destroying natural forests and habitats. We present a current evaluation of Elm species' genetic resources and a survey on their gene conservation, management, and gaps of knowledge. The analysis is based on an established interactive database. A special indicator, reduced area, was derived by considering the share of *Ulmus* species in the stands. The most widely distributed species occupying larger area is *Ulmus minor*, with a reduced area of 7145 ha, followed by *Ulmus laevis* (1630 ha) and *Ulmus glabra* (292 ha) (Table).

Total and reduced area of natural stands of *Ulmus* species in Bulgaria

Species	Total area (ha)	Natural stands	Reduced (area1), natural stands	Origin: coppice vs seed stands
<i>Ulmus glabra</i>	1589.6	1575.3	291.73	68 %; 32 %
<i>Ulmus laevis</i>	6699.3	6610.5	1629.75	83 %; 17 %
<i>Ulmus minor</i>	30148.6	29281.3	7145.4	93.5%; 6.5 %

The species have different patterns of distribution. While *U. minor* and *U. glabra* occur in all floristic regions of Bulgaria (with the exception of Slavyanka for *U. glabra*), *U. laevis* occupies more specific ecological niche along the larger rivers. Four new floristic regions could be added to the distribution of this species – Danube plain, Forebalkan, Sredna gora and Mesta river valley (paper in preparation).

The participation share of the target species in the stands was up to 30% in 70-80% of the cases (Fig. 1). Most stands of all species occur within the altitudinal range up to 200 m (more than 80%; fig. 2). Also, most genetic resources were concentrated within the three age classes up to 60 years (fig. 3).

The health conditions varied depending on different factors, most important of them being the management history. The total area designed for in situ conservation is more than 200 ha, and there are three clone collections with more than 80 clones.

Ulmus species in Bulgaria are traditionally highly valued but still neglected by forestry professionals. We outlined the state of the art and existing gap knowledges and drew focus on areas that should be addressed in the near future, including detailed study on the genetic diversity of natural populations.